

Arab Events And Issues As Reflected In The News Programs On The Arab Satellite News Channels In Ordering The Priorities Of The Iraqi Academic Elites, Libya And Lebanon As A Model (A Survey)

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 06, 2021

Accepted:
June 06, 2021

Keywords :

Satellite News, Arab
Events And Issues,
Media

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4904725

Abstract

The Arab news channels are interested in presenting different media messages based on differing opinions and viewpoints by presenting news programs that occupy a time space within the programmatic map of satellite channels, in order to inform the public of what is happening locally, regionally and internationally, in terms of dealing with controversial issues by analysis, interpretation and identification Their causes and who is responsible for their creation, since these programs are directed to the public in general, but they are directed primarily to the academic elite (the elite), due to their influence over the content of these programs and because of their pivotal role in creating public opinion in terms of actively dealing with events, positions and visions related to current events.

Introduction

In light of the media competition between Arab news channels and direct broadcasts to attract the audience to them, these satellite channels sought to discuss issues and events by presenting a daily and constant news program within the programmatic map, and most of the time the content provided by this type of program does not differ, but the difference lies in the direction of addressing The program addresses the issues raised in terms of presentation and delay in order to form their agendas towards those issues and the topics associated with them, so the research problem was the main question: standing on the role of news programs in the Arab news satellite channels in arranging the priorities of the Iraqi academic elites, and a number of questions stem from it:

- 1- How often do you watch news programs on Arab news channels?
- 2- What is the respondents' interest in the issues presented by this type of program?
- 3- What is the order of the respondents for the topics related to the issues, according to the weight percentage and the weighted mean?

Research importance

The importance of the time period in which the research was conducted, as it represents an important research requirement, as it coincides with the escalation of turmoil in Arab issues characterized by the continuous development of their events, and in light of the growing role played by news programs of interest among those who follow this type of programs at the expense of other programs.

Research aims

- 1- Monitoring the limits of the respondents' interest in the Libyan and Lebanese issues
- 2- Determining the variables affecting the respondents in arranging their priorities
- 3- Knowing the respondents' proposals from their point of view that should be available in this type of program.

Research Methodology

This research is a descriptive research that aims to study the relationship between the variables present in the phenomenon in question, and this research depends on the survey method as the most appropriate scientific method for collecting field data for a particular phenomenon and explaining it and explaining the correlational relationships between its variables in order to form the basic base of data and information required in the field Specialization.

Research tools:

Questionnaire: The study relied on a questionnaire as a tool to collect data. The field study form included (12) questions and was divided into four axes (demography and facts, presentation, methods of dialogue and setting the agenda, issues and topics).

Search ranges

1. Time domain: The time range has been determined for the period from 1/7/2020 to 3/30/2021, which is the period in which the research form was prepared and submitted to the experts for arbitration, and then the questionnaire was prepared. It was distributed and entered into the computer through the statistical program spss, and the results were extracted in the form of Scales.
2. Spatial domain: represented in three Iraqi universities (Baghdad, Al-Nahrain, Al-Mustansiriya).
3. The human field: the faculty members of the political science faculties in these universities represent those who hold a scientific degree and the scientific title and continue to teach and who possess the scientific ability and follow-up on the situation. And dealing with research requirements and their belonging to different political and intellectual trends, which represents a diversity in conducting field research and ensuring the availability of a measure. High awareness and awareness they have in analyzing the issues under discussion, and being a framed community that is easily accessible.

The research sample

It was determined according to systematic scientific steps, by choosing a studied sample from the available community, and by following the method of equal distribution by dividing the number of items in the total sample by the classes of the studied community, then choosing the terms. From the sample of political science teachers in these universities on purpose and by chance, as the sample size was determined according to a scientific standard approved in field studies, so that we have the number of the community as the total number of political science teachers in the three universities is (220) teaching and teaching, and that each 132 individuals in homogeneous communities representing (200) people and with a degree of confidence (0.95) (1). (35) Questionnaires are distributed for each college and a comprehensive inventory of all departments.

$$35 = \frac{35,2 \times \text{Searched for each college}}{3} = \frac{105,6}{3} = 105,6 = \frac{160 \times 132}{200} = \text{Sample volume}$$

Statistical data processing:

After completing the field study data collection, it was coded by entering it into the computer, extracting the results using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program, and using statistical tests: simple frequencies, percentage, weighted mean, and Ka2 test to study the statistical significance of the relationship between the two variables from the nominal variables and calculate the sample size equation.

Validity and reliability tests

Honesty: The form was presented to a group of arbitrators* from professors specialized in the field of media and political science to verify the internal consistency of the questions in the form).

Stability: The questionnaire was re-applied to 10% of the respondents, and the value of the reliability coefficient was (90), which indicates its ability and suitability to measure the research variables.

Procedural definitions

Arab events and issues: the two cases, Libya and Lebanon, and related topics, which were identified in terms of the follow-up of the news programs in those two satellite channels.

Arab Satellite News: This research is represented by the Arabic channels Al-Hadath and Al-Mayadin.

Iraqi Academic Elites: Faculty Members of the Faculties of Political Science in the Universities of Baghdad, Al-Nahrain, and Al-Mustansiriya.

Theoretical framework

Libya is witnessing a state of political instability as a result of the crisis that extended since 2011 after the fall of the Gaddafi regime and the spread of internal war between various parties supported by regional and international parties. Libya entered the tenth year after the fall of the Gaddafi regime within the framework of the protest movement that swept the Arab region since the beginning of 2011. In Lebanon, the state of political instability extends since the assassination of former Prime Minister Rafik Hariri in 2005, as the Lebanese parties were unable to achieve a state of political stability as a result of internal conflicts and their link to the conflict in the Middle East region (2). As the civil war continued in Libya with the beginning of July of 2020 between the Government of National Accord that takes Tripoli as its capital and is internationally recognized and supported by Qatar, Turkey and Italy, and the forces that depart from Tobruk in eastern Libya supported by General Khalifa Haftar, who leads the so-called The Libyan National Army is supported by Egypt, the UAE and Russia, and after strenuous efforts by the United Nations and the major powers in the international system in the framework of the numerous Geneva rounds, it was agreed to appoint 75 representatives of the various Libyan

parties, who will be tasked with choosing a new presidential council and appointing a new transitional government. An end to the state of division and civil war. On February 5, 2021, a vote was made to appoint a new presidential council of 3 people, and a new transitional government was formed in mid-March under the leadership of Abdul Hamid al-Dabaiba, after the dismissal of Fayez al-Sarraj's government, and it is the responsibility of the new government to unify the Libyan army and eliminate Terrorist organizations in Libya, stopping external interference in Libyan affairs, restoring control over energy sources and re-production in all regions of Libya, and embarking on the process of rebuilding what was destroyed by the civil war. The second of the twenty-first century (3).

As for Lebanon, with the beginning of July of last year, the economic crisis related to the political crisis intensified, as the protest movement that erupted in October of the year 2019 contributed to the resignation of the government of Saad Hariri and the election of a new government headed by Hassan Diab, but it faced crises on various levels, most notably the economic crisis. The decline in the value of the Lebanese currency and the government's loss of the ability to pay the salaries of its employees, in addition to the inability of citizens to withdraw their financial balances from banks, which contributed to the outbreak of a major political crisis that reflected on the economic and social side significantly, and the Lebanese government tried to seek the assistance of the International Monetary Fund to help Lebanon, with the hand The negotiations were suspended in July of last year after the escalation of the political and economic crisis in Lebanon, and this contributed to the continuing state of political instability in Lebanon in light of the internal struggle of wills between the Lebanese political forces supported by regional parties, especially the Hariri axis and its allies supported by Saudi Arabia and some The Arab countries, the axis of Hezbollah and Michel Aoun, supported by Iran and its allies in the region, are alarming The matter is the continuation of the state of political instability and the loss of the ability to form a government capable of facing the challenges facing Lebanon at various levels (4).

The media field for using the agenda theory:

The basic concept of agenda setting theory is that the media may not succeed all the time in informing people about how they are thinking, but do they succeed efficiently in informing people of what they are thinking? What To Think About (5), definitions and opinions on the concept of agenda setting by researchers have varied, and the concept of setting interests has been called (a classification of political issues according to the importance viewed by a ranking of political issues according to Importance, or as a list of issues. And the events that are considered at some time as arranged according to their importance) (6), and there are those who see (the process by which events turn into prominent issues around which opinions for support and opposition crystallize) (7).

The concept of setting the agenda was linked to some concepts (8):

1- Salience: It is the main concept in priority-setting research, which is the indication of the emergence of certain issues in the news program through the volume of information presented about them, as well as the position the case occupies in coverage among other issues, which is reflected in the emergence of these issues. And the increase in interest in it in the agenda of the public exposed to the program (9), i.e. the degree of relative importance that the public gives to the issue within the list of issues presented, and the extent of its significance and the impact of this issue on them (10) There are three components for the emergence of issues among the public, as follows (11):

A- Social salience, the evaluation of the individual relates to the importance of the issue and its implications and the extent of its benefits to society.

B - Personal salience, the proximity of the issue to the self-interest of the individual, as well as the extent of his attention to it and its significance in relation to him.

T- The special prominence of the issue in itself is arousal, and it is related to the features of the case and its ability to provoke the individual and attract his attention.

2- Drawing interest or directing interest ((Priming): a social, cognitive and psychological term, which can be defined as the influence of a specific context on the understanding and interpretation of information, and that the stimulus that was presented in the news program in a specific manner will be prominent in the mind of the individual the same method that was presented With it, then it is an explanation of the psychological process of the effects of setting the agenda)) (12), as the channel presents through its news programs certain issues and neglects others, and the individuals evaluate the external reality accordingly, but Priming does not stand at the first level of the effects of setting the agenda, but rather contributes In forming the opinions of individuals and their attitudes towards the issue, which is called the second level of setting the agenda (13).

3- Attention & Awareness: The increased attention to an issue on television leads to greater awareness of it than other issues to which attention is less focused, and then it becomes at the top of the target audience's priority list (14).

4- Emphasis & Concern: Emphasis leads to increased interest in issues (15), and one of the closely related titles for setting the agenda is the issue of the issue cycle, which refers to the process of fluctuation in terms of the emergence and disappearance of issues in the agenda of the program and its reflection on Appearing and

disappearing into the agenda of the masses 'issues, as an issue appears on the agenda of the masses' priorities due to its intense appearance from the channel's coverage of its news and dialogue programs, and then the degree of interest in it gradually diminished among the masses with the diminution of coverage and treatment, to be replaced by another issue that takes a greater extent of attention to coverage, to be reflected once. Another is on the level of interest of the masses, and thus the process of appearance and disappearance remains between the agenda of the program and the agenda of the masses, while the interest cycle is defined (16), and this process goes through several stages, namely: the pre-issue phase, then the stage of discovery and high emergence, followed by a phase A sense of the increasing prominence of the issue, and then the phase of the gradual fading of individuals's interest in the case, and finally the post-case phase and the prelude to the beginning of the emergence of another case.

5-Zero-Sum: After increasing the use of the time series method in the agenda setting research to track the extent of the audience's awareness of the importance of an issue at different time periods, as the zero sum model appeared, as a response to that method that neglects that there is a limited comprehension capacity for some Issues, which leads to a competition between issues and events to get the public's attention, as the rise of one issue in the public's agenda leads to neglecting another issue, and this is called the zero sum (17).

6- Weaver and Elliot used the term filtering more than setting the agenda, as they indicated that the latter term carries with it the meaning of creating or making issues on the part of the media, while the new term refers precisely to the nature of the role played by the communicator in choosing between the issues presented to him Through the various sources and passing judgments on the size of the coverage that each of them is entitled to (18).

7- In the nineties, Roessler introduced the concept of Agenda Designing, which in turn indicates that the importance that the individual attaches to certain issues is no longer limited to the influence of television alone, but a number of other factors intervene in that process such as: personal experiences, attitudes, and personal contact, And the perceptions of the group to which the individual belongs, in addition to presenting the issue through other media, all of these factors would contribute to the cognitive construction of the issue in the mind of the individual who, in turn, assesses the impact of all these factors together to put in the end his judgment and his personal appreciation of the importance of these issues (19).

8-Around the same period, McCombs and show et.al added a new concept, which is that Agenda Melding is a process that occurs all the time in society and represents an important part of the efforts made by the individual in order to learn more about the groups in which he is interested and wish to join This process takes place through the individual use of the media that are related to these social groups, and then this results in the mixing of the individual's personal agenda with that of that group, which ultimately leads to the mixing of the agenda of individuals who are exposed to a group of issues together, otherwise these individuals feel isolated from Their communities (20).

9-The concept of the unifying agenda Agenda Melding, which indicates that individuals use a number of media to relate to each other, and that followers of any group's agenda is a continuous social process when a person participates in the topic presented on television. This is a kind of social nutrition that People have been able to feel connected to one another by engaging in a public agenda (21).

Research results:

First Axis: Demography and Facts:

A- Those that follow news programs:

1- By gender: the respondents 'answers were divided into (90) male respondents, at a rate of (60%), as they represented the largest part of the sample and (60) female respondents, at a rate of (40%).

2- According to the university: The distribution of the respondents, whose number is (150) who follow this type of programs for the two research channels, for the universities by the two rivers (66) respondents and by (44%), and (52) respondents from Baghdad (34.7%), and Al-Mustansiriya. (32) Respondents with a rate of (21.3%).

3- By academic degree: the respondents were distributed according to their academic degree into a teacher (56) respondents with a percentage of (37.3%), an assistant professor (46) respondents with a percentage of (30%), an assistant teacher (34) respondents with a percentage of (22.7%), and a professor (14) of respondents, at a rate of (9.3%).

B-Those who do not follow the news programs:

1- By gender: the answers of female respondents were distributed by (60%) and males by (40%).

2- According to the university: The respondents who are (10) who do not follow this type of program are distributed to the two research channels for the universities of Baghdad by (40%), and the two rivers and Al-Mustansiriya (30%) are both.

Exposure

First: The extent of watching Arab news channels: Respondents' responses were distributed about watching Arab news channels. I always watch (52.5%) and sometimes watch (41.2%) and those who do not. Viewing rate (6.3%).

Second: The extent to which the respondents followed the news programs of Al-Mayadeen and Al-Arabiya channels Al-Hadath: The results were:

Most of them: by (62.8%) Al-Arabiya Al-Hadath TV and by (37.2%) Al-Mayadeen TV.

Sometimes: (43.8%) Al-Arabiya Al-Hadath TV and (56.2%) Al-Mayadeen TV.

The respondents' answers showed an increase in the follow-up rate in the respondents' answers, indicating that they are a source for obtaining information about the Libyan and Lebanese situation.

Third: In the methods of dialogue and setting the agenda: the responses of the respondents were divided and five higher ranks according to the viewpoint of the respondents in Al-Arabiya Al-Hadath channel, and the results were as follows:

- 1- These programs seek to highlight the responsibility of the concerned authorities towards the topic presented for dialogue and discussion: This paragraph ranked first with a weight of (96.7) and a weighted average of (2.9).
- 2- It came in second place with a weight of (90) and a weighted average of (2.7). Each of these programs seeks to push the public in a specific direction in their dealings with issues related to the topic presented in these programs. . The media handling of the issue at hand highlights the editorial policy of the program, in agreement with or against.
- 3- These programs tend to host specific analysts and experts inclined to the editorial policy of the channel: This paragraph came in third place with a weight ratio (86.7) and a weighted average (2.6).
- 4- Exchange of views, even if they differ in that: fourth place with a weight ratio (80) and a weighted average (2,4).

The results for Al-Mayadeen TV were as follows:

- 1- Media treatment of the topic at hand sheds light on the editorial policy of the program with approval or against: This paragraph came in first place with a weighted average (90) and a weight ratio (90).
- 2- These programs seek to push the audience in a specific direction in their approach to issues related to the topic presented in these programs: This paragraph came in second place with a weighted percentage (83.3) and a weighted average (2.5).
- 3- These programs tend to host specific analysts and experts inclined to the editorial policy of the channel: The channel ranked third with a weight ratio (80) and a weighted average (2,4).
- 4- These programs seek to highlight the responsibility of the concerned authorities towards the topic under discussion and discussion: This paragraph came in fourth place with a weight ratio of (76.7) and a weighted average (2.3).
- 5- The exchange of views, even if they differed in that: it came in the fifth place with a percentage weight (70) and a weighted average (2.1).

And it became clear from the results of the respondents' answers that some paragraphs of this question had similar choices for them and according to their point of view, with different weighting ratios and the weighted means for these paragraphs for both channels. As well as for other paragraphs with low weights.

Fourth: Methods for presenting the dialogue: The respondents' answers were divided into several options according to the follow-up of the news programs of the Al-Arabiya Al-Hadath channels and Al-Mayadin according to the arithmetic average and weighting rates on Al-Arabiya Al-Hadath channel as follows:

- 1- It ranked first by obtaining the highest weights among the other methods (90) and a weighted average (2.7) for each enthusiastic presentation style by relying on stimulating the audience's feelings, speed of performance, repetition of the axes' movement, and the method. Viewable using psychological factors.
- 2- The scientific presentation method where the axes begin by mentioning numbers and statistics and using graphs: it came in second place with a weight ratio (86.7) and a weighted average (2,6).
- 3- Method of combining the previous methods: it came in third place with a weighted ratio (83.3) and a weighted average (2.5).

And that is in the Al-Mayadeen channel, according to the following:

- 1- The method of presentation using psychological factors: it ranked first with a weight percentage (90) and a weighted average (2.7).
- 2- The enthusiastic presentation style that depends on arousing the feelings of the audience, the speed of performance, and the frequency of movement of the axes: it came in second place with a weight ratio of (83,3) and a weighted average (2.5).
- 3- The scientific presentation method where the axes start by mentioning numbers and statistics and using graphs: it came in third place with a weight percentage (80) and a weighted average (2.4).

It was clear from the previous results that there is a discrepancy in the respondents' answers in their selection according to the percentage weights and the weighted means of the methods of presenting news programs, with

the exception of the section on the method of presentation using psychology. Factors with the highest weight ratio and weighted average for both channels.

Fifth: The influencing variables were distributed and the agenda was set for this type of program according to their meanings and percentage weights as follows:

1- The special prominence of the proposed topic and its ability to motivate and draw the public's attention to the program: it ranked first according to the percentage weight (90) and among the highest weights for other paragraphs and a weighted average (2.7).

2- The relative importance of the issue presented in the program in terms of focus on it and repetition on it at length: This paragraph came in second place on the basis of the weighted ratio (86.7) and the weighted average (2.6).

3- The direction of the program in relation to the topic at hand: It ranked third in terms of percentage of weight (83.3) and weighted average (2.5).

4- Timing and presentation of the lawsuit: fourth place on the basis of percentage weight (80) and a weighted average (2,4).

5- The degree of interest in the issue raised by the public (psychological and geographical proximity): it ranked fifth in terms of its weight ratio (73.3) and a weighted average (2.2).

6- Who are the guests participating in the program: ranked sixth with a percentage weight of (50) and a weighted average (1.5).

It was clear from the previous results that the three most important variables that affected the setting of the agenda of the news program are the relative importance of the topic in question and the program's orientation towards it and its visibility through focusing the editorial policy of the program and linking it to the channel. By providing time space for discussion and repetition, which helps the agenda of the program, and the ability to make a significant impact and direct the audience. Realizing the relative importance of some issues at the expense of others, as the cumulative effect of media messages about an issue, in turn, affects the public's agenda by including it within the circle of its interests, its importance, and the impact of this issue on them.

Sixth: On the question of the respondents about the proposals that should be available for this type of program:

1- The neutrality of the interviewer (program presenter) in dealing with the subject raised with the dialogue parties without prejudice to one party: he ranked first with a percentage of (19.3%) and (34) recurrences. Depending on their view of any issue at hand, the public may judge it as biased towards one party. One of the parties to the dialogue, not the professional interlocutor, is his commitment to impartiality in dealing with the parties, even if he agrees with one party and not the other, and that the successful interlocutor is the one who adheres to the ethics of dialogue and understands the responsibility of the speech, rises from personal agendas, separates opinion from information and stands on one space without discrimination Against different currents. The accuracy and integrity of every word in the program is verified (22).

2- Distribution of time equally among the parties to the dialogue: it came in second place with a ratio of (18.2%) and (32) iterations.

3- Avoidance of emotional style by the interviewees and interlocutors during their discussion of the issue at hand: it came in third place with a rate of (14.7%) and (26) recurrences.

4- The use of more specialized guests for dialogue and discussion of topics related to the issue at hand: it ranked fourth with (14.2%) and (25) iteratively that the guest was well chosen in a way that strengthens the news program's strategy for the issue at hand and those who have the ability to interpret and analyze on the topic related to the case posed.

5- Accurately presenting the case, getting acquainted with it, analyzing it, and proposing solutions regarding it: it came in the fifth place with a rate of (12.5%) and (22) iterations.

6- The personality of the presenters of this type of programs is distinguished and have the ability to manage the dialogue: it ranked sixth with a rate of (11.4%) and (20) iterations.

7- Highlighting both the role of the official and the citizen towards the issue presented for dialogue and discussion: It ranked seventh with a rate of (9.7%) and (17) repeatedly.

Therefore, the interlocutors require moderation in the distribution of roles and timelines for each of the parties to the dialogue, as well as moderation in enthusiasm and emotional equilibrium. We often see excessive enthusiasm, which leads to the deviation of the dialogue from its main topic, and that the dialogue does not mean highlighting the verbal abilities of the interlocutor only, but rather it means It is equally important to listen to the other and understand his intentions until his speech ends.

Seventh: Concerning the issues of most interest to the two channels, the Lebanese and Libyan issues that occupied the interest of the respondents from political science professors of the three universities were the Lebanese issue, as Al-Arabiya Al-Hadath received the highest percentage weight (95) and a weighted average (1.9), while in Al-Mayadin channel a percentage weight (85). And a weighted medium (1.7), while the Libyan

case in Al-Arabiya Al-Hadath channel has a percent weight (85) and a weighted medium (1.7), and in Al-Mayadeen channel a percentage weight (80) and a weighted medium (1.6).

Eighth: On the topics related to the Libyan case, the respondents' answers came according to the arithmetic mean and the percentage weights of the Arabic channels Al-Hadath and Al-Majadin as follows:

A-Al-Arabiya Al-Hadath channel:

1- Fears and warnings of the representative of the United Nations Secretary-General in Libya Stephanie Williams about the escalation of fighting in the Libyan cities: This paragraph came in first place according to the percentile weight (88) and among the highest weights for the other paragraphs and a weighted average (4,4).

2- The international and regional welcome of the Egyptian President Abdel Fattah Al-Sisi's initiative in the (Cairo Declaration) initiative, after Egypt's concerns about the turbulent situation in Libya: it ranked second according to the percentile weight (86) and a weighted average (4,3), and by using the chi square to find out the significance of the difference regarding This paragraph, according to the statistical test, the results showed an indication in the interest of the Arab juvenile.

3- It was ranked third with a percentage weight (84) and a weighted mean (4.2) each of the following paragraphs:

European and Russian efforts to emphasize the Paris and Berlin conferences regarding the convergence of views between the two sides of the Libyan crisis and the Turkish military and logistical support for the Libyan Government of National Accord (Fayez Al-Sarraj) by sending mercenary fighters from the Syrian factions loyal to it to fight alongside the Government of National Accord (17300) Syrian mercenaries, and using the Kai Square To identify the significance of the difference regarding this paragraph, and according to the statistical test, the results showed a significant benefit in the interest of the Arabic event.

4- Emphasis on the implementation of Security Council Resolution No. 1970 of 2011 and subsequent resolutions to respect and implement the embargo on the supply of arms to Libya based on the Berlin Conference: It ranked fourth according to the weight percentile (80) and a weighted mean (4), and using the chi-square to identify the significance of the difference regarding this paragraph, and according to the statistical test, the results showed a significant benefit in the interest of the Arabic event.

5- Calling the Parliament and the Presidency Council to announce the ceasefire initiative, the resumption of oil exports, and the activation of the political process: it ranked fifth with a percentage weight (68) and a weighted average (3,4).

B- The respondents' answers to Al-Mayadeen Channel on issues related to the Libyan case, according to the following:

1- Concerns and warnings of the representative of the Secretary-General of the United Nations in Libya, Stephanie Williams, about the escalation of the pace of fighting in Libyan cities: This paragraph ranked first according to the percentage weight (90), and among the highest weights for the other paragraphs and a weighted mean (4.5), using the chi-square In order to know the significance of the difference regarding this paragraph, the results showed a function of the field interest.

2- Turkish military and logistical support for the Libyan Government of National Accord (Fayez al-Sarraj) by sending mercenary fighters from the loyal Syrian factions to fight alongside the Government of National Accord (17,300) Syrian mercenaries: it ranked second with a weight of (88) percent and a weight of (4,4), and by using Chi-square, to find out the significance of the difference regarding this paragraph, the results showed a function of interest of the fields.

3- It ranked third with a percentage weight (82) and a weighted average (4.1) each of the following paragraphs: European and Russian efforts by affirming the Paris and Berlin conferences regarding the convergence of viewpoints between the two sides of the Libyan crisis and the international and regional welcome to the Egyptian President Abdel Fattah El-Sisi's initiative in the (Cairo Declaration) initiative, after Egypt's concerns about the turbulent situation in Libya.

4- Inviting Parliament and the Presidential Council to announce the ceasefire initiative, resume oil exports and activate the political process: It ranked fourth with a weight percentage (78) and a weighted mean (3.9), and using the chi-square to identify the significance of the difference regarding this paragraph and according to the statistical test the results showed A function of the field interest.

5- Emphasizing the implementation of Security Council Resolution No. 1970 of 2011 and subsequent decisions respecting and applying the embargo on arms supplies to Libya, based on the Berlin Conference: it ranked fifth according to percentage weight (74) and a weighted average (3.7).

Ninth: Regarding the topics related to the Lebanese issue, the respondents' answers came according to the arithmetic circles and the percentage weights of the Arabic channels Al-Hadath and Al-Mayadeen as follows:

A- Al-Arabiya Al-Hadath channel:

1- Mass demonstrations and protests swept through Beirut, the capital, and the governorates against the ruling elite in Lebanon after the Council of Ministers approved the imposition of a tax package on oil derivatives, cigarettes, and communications (WhatsApp): This paragraph ranked first according to the percentage weight (94) and among the highest weights of other paragraphs and the middle Weighted (4,7), and by using chi-square to identify the significance of the difference, and according to the statistical test, the results showed a function in the interest of the Arab juvenile.

2- The outbreak of confrontations with the army and security forces with the protesters in front of the cabinet headquarters and government headquarters after the continuation of the general strike in public institutions and the educational sector: it ranked second according to the weight percentile (90) and a weighted mean (4.5), and using the chi-square, the results showed a function In the interest of the Arab event.

3- Providing Arab and international aid for the relief of the people of Lebanon and visiting European leaders of the impact of the Beirut Port bombing and the repercussions it caused, the loss of billions of dollars and severe material damage: it ranked third with a weight of a percentage (84) and a weight of (4.2), and by using chi-square and according to the statistical test, the results showed a function in the interest of Arab juvenile.

4- The protesters' rejection of the reform paper announced by former Prime Minister Saad Hariri at a press conference and giving himself 72 hours to resolve the crisis or submit his resignation: it ranked fourth according to the percentile weight (80) and a weighted average (4).

5- The resignation of the Diab government and its transformation into a caretaker government after the continuing protests demanding its resignation: It ranked fifth with a percentage weight (74) and a weighted average (3.7).

6- Saad Hariri's announcement of the resignation of his government and the assignment of Hassan Diab: It ranked sixth with a percentage weight (68) and a weighted average (3,4).

B- Al-Mayadeen channel:

1- Mass demonstrations and protests swept through Beirut, the capital, and the governorates against the ruling elite in Lebanon after the Council of Ministers approved the imposition of a tax package on oil derivatives, cigarettes, and communications (WhatsApp): This paragraph ranked first according to the percentile weight (90) and among the highest weights of other paragraphs and the middle Weighted (4,5).

2- The protesters rejected the reform paper announced by former Prime Minister Saad Hariri in a press conference and gave himself 72 hours to resolve the crisis or submit his resignation: it ranked second according to the weight percentile (80) and weighted mean (4.2), using chi-square and according to the test The statistical results showed a function in favor of the fields.

3- The resignation of the Diab government and its transfer to the caretaker government after the protests demanded its resignation: It came in third place with a percentage weight (78) and a weighted average (3.9), and by using the chi-square and according to the statistical test, the results showed an indication of the interest of the fields.

4- It ranked fourth according to the percentage weight (72) and a weighted average (3.6) of each of the paragraphs: the outbreak of confrontations with the army and security forces with the protesters in front of the Council of Ministers and government headquarters after the continuation of the general strike in public institutions and the educational sector and the announcement of Saad Hariri The resignation of his government and the assignment of Hassan Diab, and by using the Kay square to find out the significance of the difference regarding the clause of Saad Hariri's announcement of the resignation of his government, and according to the statistical test, the results showed an indication of the interest of al-Mayadin.

5- Providing Arab and international aid for the relief of the people of Lebanon and visiting European leaders in the impact of the Beirut port explosion and the repercussions it caused, the loss of billions of dollars and severe material damage: It ranked fifth with a weight of (70) percent and a weight of (3.9).

Conclusions

1- Emphasizing the relative importance of the issue at hand, in terms of focusing on it and repeating it intensively, is one of the most important variables in setting the agenda of the program. The public's knowledge of certain issues comes in terms of adopting the news program and focusing on them in presenting them in order to generate conviction of the relative importance of the issues at hand and to increase thinking about them.

2- Emphasizing the impartiality of the interlocutor (the presenter of the program) in his handling of the issue at hand with the parties to the dialogue without prejudice to one of the most important proposals that should be available for this type of program, as well as the equal distribution of time between the parties to the dialogue.

3- The emergence of each of the two styles of enthusiastic presentation, based on its reliance on stimulating the feelings of the audience, speed in performance, frequent movement of the axes, and the method of presentation using psychological factors.

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